

THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING GEOGRAPHY IS ONE OF THE CORE DISCIPLINES OF HIGHER GEOGRAPHICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The solution of this problem is facilitated by the fact that the educational material corresponds to one lesson, and various methods of orientation and organization of cognitive activity of students are used in the text.*

A great help to the teacher in preparing the lesson is provided by the program, where a list of what students should know and be able to do is given for each topic. First of all, the main scientific and ideological content of the lesson is highlighted. The educational material is divided into semantic parts.

In each part, the main, basic educational material is determined (leading concepts, basic facts, the most significant cause-and-effect relationships and dependencies, important patterns) and auxiliary.

Characteristics of the economic and geographical position of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Description of the relief, water and natural resources of the country. Analysis of the type of reproduction and population density. Analysis of the level of development of industry and foreign economic relations.

The teacher determines which educational material will be studied with his help, and which one independently. The previously received training of students in geography and other academic subjects is taken into account. For each semantic part, it is planned to work with various sources of geographical knowledge. The most difficult questions of the topic are explained by the teacher. Selection of teaching methods and tools.

In most cases, not all the textbook material is explained in class due to limited time, some of it is studied by students at home. In high school, the proportion of this material increases. A simple topic can be fully studied by students on their own.

Key words: *Geography, educational material, nature, independent work, education, training, teaching methods.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГЕОГРАФИИ — ОДНА ИЗ ПРОФИЛИРУЮЩИХ ДИСЦИПЛИН ВЫСШЕГО ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *Рассматриваются вопросы решение этой задачи облегчается тем, что учебный материал соответствующие одному уроку, и в тексте использованы разнообразные приемы ориентировки и организации познавательной деятельности учащихся. Большую помощь учителю при подготовке урока оказывает программа, где по каждой теме дан перечень того, что учащиеся должны знать и уметь. Прежде всего, выделяется основное научное и мировоззренческое содержание урока. Учебный материал разделяется на смысловые части.*

В каждой части определяется главный, основной учебный материал (ведущие понятия, основные факты, наиболее существенные причинно-следственные связи и зависимости, важные закономерности) и вспомогательный. Характеристика экономико-географического положения Республики Узбекистан. Описание рельефа, водных и природных ресурсов страны. Анализ типа воспроизводства и плотности населения. Анализ уровня развития промышленности и внешнеэкономических связей.

Учитель определяет, какой учебный материал будет изучаться с его помощью, а какой самостоятельно. Учитывается ранее полученная подготовка учащихся по географии и другим учебным предметам. По каждой смысловой части предусматривается работа с различными источниками географических знаний. Наиболее сложные вопросы темы объясняются учителем. Отбор методов и средств обучения.

В большинстве случаев не весь материал учебника объясняется на уроке из-за ограниченного времени, часть его изучается учащимися дома. В старших классах доля этого материала возрастает. Несложная тема может полностью изучаться учащимися самостоятельно.

Ключевые слова: География, учебный материал, природа, самостоятельная работа, образования, обучения, методика преподавания.

INTRODUCTION

In the Address, the Head of state defined further goals and set the most important tasks aimed at ensuring a consistent increase in the level of well-being and well-being of the country's population.

On December 29, 2020, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev addressed another Message to the Oliy Majlis, and in his person - to the people of Uzbekistan. One of the central places in the President's speech was occupied by the issues of conducting an effective foreign policy capable of providing the necessary conditions for the implementation of a large-scale program of reform and modernization of all spheres of life of society and the state[1].

To this end, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev pointed out the need to improve the republic's foreign policy strategy and adopt an updated concept of activities in this area. At the same time, the importance of ensuring the consistency of Uzbekistan's open, proactive and constructive foreign policy was emphasized.

In general, in recent years, our country has achieved a qualitative shift in the international arena. Uzbekistan strives to become a responsible and predictable partner, ready to solve the most pressing problems of both the regional and global agenda in a constructive and open dialogue, creating the necessary favorable external conditions for the implementation of a large-scale program of reform and modernization of our country, primarily for the benefit of the people living in Uzbekistan[2].

In this regard, the approval of the Concept of Foreign Policy Activity in the new edition is an objective necessity and is designed to lay a solid foundation for an effective foreign policy aimed at ensuring the further dynamic growth of Uzbekistan in post-pandemic realities.

We are talking about the global reputation, geographical structure and education of Uzbekistan. Teaching geography involves not only giving solid knowledge of the subject, but also promoting the education and development of students on geographical material, and contributing to the formation of the student's personality. The theory of education is developed by pedagogy. Therefore, the technique is closely related to it. The development of education issues in geography lessons is based on the provisions of pedagogy[3].

Teaching any subject is impossible without taking into account the age characteristics of students, their physiological and psychological development. The material being studied should be within the student's strength, arouse a certain interest. Therefore, psychology is of great

importance for the development of methods of teaching geography. The data of pedagogical and developmental psychology on the psychophysiological characteristics of students of different ages are taken into account in the selection of content and the choice of forms and methods of teaching geography.

Psychology provides the methodology with data on the characteristics of memory, thinking of students of different ages, on differences in the perception of theoretical and factual material. A special role of pedagogical psychology belongs to the development of learning motives, cognitive interests in relation to school geography. In connection with the increase in the content of school geography of theoretical knowledge, the connection between the methodology of teaching geography and logic is being strengthened.

A special need for this arose in connection with a clear allocation in the program of scientific concepts that represent one of the forms of thinking, as well as. with the task of the school "to teach students to learn", to instill in them the skills and abilities of self-education. To acquire knowledge, students must be able to use such methods of logical thinking as analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison, generalization, etc.

Like any branch of knowledge, the methodology of teaching geography is closely related to practice, which has a direct impact on the development of science. The methodology equips teachers with the theory of teaching and educating students. The study of the socio-economic conditions for the development of our country, the state of basic science, and the practice of teaching geography at school makes it possible to identify urgent problems that require scientific development and solutions.

Like any other branch of knowledge, the methodology of teaching geography as a science has developed methods for studying the process of teaching geography. The teacher of geography must have the knowledge and skills of research work according to the methodology of the subject. This is necessary for evaluating one's own work, studying the experience of other teachers, self-education and creative search. Dialectical materialism is the universal method of cognizing reality, including the process of teaching geography. This is the methodological basis of the methodology for teaching geography[4-7].

Dialectical materialism requires an approach to the study of the process of education, upbringing and development as a whole; consider the learning process from the point of view of the general connection and dependence of its components and elements, as well as from the point of view of the transition of quantitative changes into qualitative ones, the disclosure of internal contradictions; consider the learning process in continuous movement, change and development.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Theoretical methods are aimed at creating generalizations, analyzing facts, and identifying patterns in the learning process. These include: system-structural analysis, typological approach, mathematical methods, historical and comparative methods. The essence of system-structural analysis is that the subject of study is considered as an integral system consisting of interacting components, and the focus is on the study of relationships and interactions between these components.

In accordance with this, when studying the process of teaching geography, links are revealed between the activities of the teacher and the student (i.e., teaching and learning), between the goals, content, methods and means of teaching, between the assimilation of knowledge, development and education of schoolchildren. System-structural analysis involves

the definition of the objectives of the lesson, in connection with the objectives, the content of training, teaching methods and techniques, educational equipment are determined.

The systematic approach is also manifested in the fact that the teacher plans and develops several lessons at once on a particular topic, defining the functions of each lesson and their relationship with each other in terms of goals, content and teaching methods, and the nature of the cognitive activity of students. With the help of the typological approach, the classification and grouping of the studied objects and phenomena is carried out.

At the same time, the essential features, signs of objects are determined, an analysis is made, and on the basis of the analysis, groups of objects and phenomena under study are distinguished. The typological approach finds application in the study of all problems of methodological science. With its help, the components of the content of school geography (knowledge, skills and abilities; worldview ideas) are singled out, teaching methods and means are classified, types of lessons are singled out, types of independent work of students, etc. A distinctive feature of the development of science at the present time is the use of the mathematical apparatus in the research process[5-7].

Precise mathematical methods began to be used to study the learning process of geography. They make it possible not only to qualitatively assess the objects under study, but also to express them quantitatively, to study in more depth the connections and dependencies between the components of the learning process (for example, on what factors does the improvement of geography teaching methods depend; what is the relationship between teaching methods and the level of knowledge and skills of schoolchildren development of their creative abilities). The essence of the historical method is that all phenomena under study must be considered in development, change in time.

This method requires that when developing the questions of the methodology of teaching geography, the experience of the past is taken into account, an analysis is made of how these processes have changed in the historical aspect, what stages have passed - only then can a forecast for the future be made. With the help of the historical method, the data of historical and methodological research are involved in the study of the problems of modern methods of teaching geography. The comparative method of research is the method of logical knowledge in general. It is possible to compare only homogeneous objects and phenomena, comparisons must be carried out according to essential features, signs. By means of comparison, a typological approach is carried out, and the objects and phenomena under study are classified[10-11].

The comparative method is also used in the study of foreign experience in teaching geography. Empirical research methods are aimed at studying the existing pedagogical experience or creating a new pedagogical experience.

To identify what exists in pedagogical practice, the following methods are used. 1. Observation of the learning process. The purpose of observation is determined, a program is developed, according to the program, facts are recorded in the process of observation, they are processed, and conclusions are drawn based on the analysis of the results obtained.

2. Questioning of teachers and students. The purpose of the survey is determined, the questionnaire is developed, the survey is conducted, the data is processed.

3. The study of school documentation (class magazines, thematic and lesson plans, circle work plans, etc.). Based on the study, certain conclusions are drawn about the organization of educational work at school.

4. Interviews. The purpose of the interview is determined, an interview is conducted, on the basis of which conclusions and generalizations are drawn. 5. Written test papers. They serve to identify the level of training of students, according to the results obtained, they judge the state of the educational process as a whole. Usually, a combination of methods is used to study the pedagogical experience of schools.

At the same time, something new is introduced into teaching - new educational material, a new method of teaching, a new means of teaching, etc. It is revealed how this new influences the quality of knowledge, the development and education of students. For the experiment, control and experimental classes are allocated, they must be the same in terms of the level of training[14].

In the experimental class, a new element of learning is introduced, in the control class, learning is conducted traditionally. Then the quality of knowledge of students in the classes is compared. To conduct a pedagogical experiment, a scientific assumption, a hypothesis is developed, the necessary educational and methodological material is prepared (new educational text, new visual aids, test papers, etc.). If the introduction of a new one contributes to the deepening of knowledge and the development of independence of children and confirms the previously stated assumption, it is recommended for implementation in a mass school.

Conducting methodological research includes the following steps:

1) the establishment of the main research problem (based on the study of literature and familiarization with the experience of the school) and its formulation; 2) putting forward a hypothesis;

3) formulation of research objectives on the way to solving the main problem and testing the hypothesis;

4) choice of research methods;

5) preparation of experimental materials necessary for solving each problem; 6) conducting an experiment;

7) formulation of the conclusions of the study;

8) showing the practical significance of the results obtained[20-22].

The study of the learning process is carried out by theoretical and empirical methods simultaneously. Empirical methods make it possible to accumulate factual material, which is processed using theoretical methods. In this case, analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, abstraction, comparison, generalization are used.

School geography has an important educational and educational value. The educational value lies in the fact that geography as a subject gives the student geographical knowledge. Every cultured, educated person needs this knowledge, and no other academic subject provides this knowledge.

This is knowledge about the Earth, its internal structure, relief, climate, waters, soils, vegetation, animals, population, natural resources, world economy, nature and economy of countries, about the World Ocean and individual oceans, about your country, etc. (A detailed list of knowledge is contained in the geography programs.)

Geography provides not only geographical knowledge, but also knowledge of other branches of science, the basics of which are not studied at school. School geography provides economic training for students, students receive a holistic view of the economy, its industries,

forms of organization, natural resources, and the world economy. It is also important in polytechnic education.

Natural resources and conditions in school geography are considered from the point of view of the possibility of their use in the economy. The importance of school geography in environmental education is great. The idea of rational nature management and nature protection runs through all geography courses. Many topics deal with environmental issues at both the global and regional and local levels.

The content of school geography includes knowledge from geology, demography, and sociology. Only geography as a subject provides cartographic training. Understand, read, know the map - these tasks are solved only in geography lessons. The ability to use a map is equivalent to such skills as reading and writing. The map is both a visual aid and a source of knowledge. The task of the teacher is to teach the student to use this source of knowledge[17].

The educational value of school geography lies not only in the fact that it provides knowledge, but also contributes to the development of skills and abilities. Skill is the ability to apply knowledge in practice. Skill is the automatic application of knowledge. In school geography, not all knowledge is brought to the level of skills and abilities. Important skills and abilities: the ability to read a map, characterize objects based on it, observe local geographical objects, use instruments and equipment, record the results of observations, process them, and make descriptions of objects based on the results of observations.

School geography contributes to the development of children's cognitive abilities, their memory, speech, observation, imagination, and thinking. At each lesson, the student enriches his speech with new words, concepts, names, he must acquire new knowledge, reproduce. He learns to compare, analyze, draw conclusions, generalize. All this contributes to the development of thinking.

School geography studies mainly distant geographical objects. It is necessary to form an image of these objects in memory. This is possible when using visual aids, which develops the imagination. Many geographical concepts can be formed by studying local geographical objects, by observation. Observation contributes to the development of observation. School geography has an important educational value.

One of the most important tasks of teaching at school is the formation of the foundations of the scientific worldview of students. It is carried out in the study of all school subjects. In this regard, the role and importance of geography as an academic subject is great. This is explained by the fact that geography studies an extremely wide range of issues related to both natural and social objects and phenomena. Other academic subjects consider objects and phenomena of only one quality (biology - the organic world of the Earth, physics - physical phenomena, chemistry - chemical transformations, social science - society) [18].

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Geography, on the other hand, is distinguished by an integrated approach to the studied objects and phenomena. Scientific worldview is a system of views and beliefs on the world around, awareness of oneself in this world. It includes groups of worldview ideas: dialectical materialistic; ideas reflecting the problem of interaction between nature and society (environmental); political and economic ideas.

The following ideas belong to the dialectical-materialist ideas:

1. Materiality of the world. The objects and phenomena studied in school geography are considered as real, from a materialistic point of view.

2. Knowledge of the world. The essence of the idea is that a person, thanks to consciousness and thinking, is able to cognize the world around him, to penetrate into the essence of the phenomena being studied. The implementation of this idea is provided by material on the history of the development of geographical science, familiarizing students with the history of the study of continents and oceans, with the latest geographical achievements and methods of geographical research.

3. Integrity and unity of the world, the universality of connections and dependencies.

This idea is most fully disclosed in the content of school geography and is reflected in such fundamental concepts as the natural and economic system. In school geography, objects, processes, phenomena are considered not in isolation from each other, but in their general connection and dependence. Students are brought to the idea of the unity and integrity of nature, the organic unity of man with nature.

4. Continuity of movement, change, development. Objects in school geography are studied not in a frozen state, but in continuous change and development. Cause-and-effect relationships and dependencies, dynamics and development, geographical patterns are revealed. Development is seen as a transition from one qualitative state to another, as an interaction of opposites. It is progressive.

5. Ecological ideas. The life of a person, society is possible under the condition of a continuous exchange of matter and energy with nature. Nature is the source of all material and spiritual benefits of man, the subject and means of man's labor. Natural resources are limited, so their careful and rational use is necessary. Anthropogenic influence on nature has reached planetary proportions. The development of nature is largely determined by human economic activity. Pollution of the natural environment has acquired global proportions, and the problem of rational use of natural resources and nature protection has arisen.

6. Political and economic ideas: the need to prevent a new world war; leading role in the world community; resolution of all disputable international issues through negotiations; solution of demographic, food and energy problems; deepening the international geographical division of labor, cooperation and specialization; economic globalization; alignment of levels of economic development of various countries and regions[21].

Patriotic education is of great importance in school geography. Of particular importance in this regard is the course of geography of Belarus, where students receive extensive knowledge about the nature, economy, and population of their country.

The teaching of all school geography courses is based on the local history principle. It means studying the geography of one's area, region and using this knowledge to study distant geographical objects, territories. When studying the geography of continents and countries, students get acquainted with domestic travelers and geographers who have made a significant contribution to the development of geography. Ultimately, the school must form a patriot, a citizen of his country. In school geography, peoples, human races, traditions, culture, world religions are studied, which contributes to the education of respect for other peoples (international education).

In geography as an academic subject, there is no place for negative aspects in relation to the way of life, customs, traditions, religions of peoples and races. All races, peoples, nations are equal and equally capable of mental activity. Aesthetic education is served by a variety of visual aids, excursions to nature and production. The task of the teacher is to show the beauty in nature and the creations of human hands. Acquaintance with major discoveries, the courage of discoverers contributes to the moral education of students. Geography as an academic subject is of great importance in labor education. Learning is mental work.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In our time, when scientific knowledge is growing like an avalanche, it is necessary to develop the habit of replenishing knowledge, teaching students to learn, and developing a culture of mental work. This goal is served by the organization of the mental activity of students in the classroom and outside of school hours.

Physical labor education is implemented in extracurricular activities (production and repair of visual aids, gardening, work in school forestries, etc.). Physical development is carried out during excursions and hiking trips.

When studying geography, students get acquainted with a variety of professions (career guidance work). Training, education and development is a single inseparable process. The task of the school is to shape the personality of a young person. The system of school geography courses Initially, students receive geographical training in elementary school when studying the subject "Man and the World" (grades 1-4), as well as the subject "Universe" or "Natural Studies" (grade 5). The subject "Man and the world" consists of three blocks: "Nature and man", "Man

and society", "Man and his health". Natural science preparation is carried out during the study of the first block.

Students are given the concept of what nature is, animate and inanimate nature, they get acquainted with seasonal changes in nature, the diversity of flora and fauna, including Uzbekistan, study the components of inanimate nature (air, water, rocks). Students get an initial understanding of what orientation is, a map, a globe, acquire some astronomical knowledge about the Sun, the Solar System, the Earth and its movement. When studying other blocks of the subject, students are given the initial system of humanitarian knowledge about man and society. Students will learn about the different types of pollution and their impact on human health.

Schoolchildren get acquainted with the map of radioactive contamination of the republic. Information is given on the history of the native land, economic activity, and ecology. Students as a whole in the subject receive initial knowledge about the system nature - society - man. The Natural History course is an integrated academic subject. It prepares the student for the future systematic study of subjects of the natural cycle - physics, chemistry, biology, astronomy, geography.

Its content in the 5th grade is mainly geographic and astronomical. The student gains knowledge about Natural History, its various bodies (stars, constellations, galaxies, etc.). The solar system is studied in sufficient detail, the structure of the Earth as a planet, the daily and annual movement of the Earth, the causes of eclipses, tides and tides are considered[10].

The surface shells of the Earth are characterized, their composition, the properties of the substances that compose them, the dynamics of the shells are considered, the concept of the biosphere and the geographical shell is given. The subject "Natural Science" (grades 4-5) is close in content to the "Natural Studies" Co. The study of geography as a separate subject begins in the 6th grade. The first systematic course in school geography is the elementary course (grades 6-7). The Elementary Course in Geography is the foundation of general physical and general socio-economic geography.

The main objective of the course is to form a system of general concepts in physical and socio-economic geography for students at the initial stage, to introduce them to the conceptual apparatus of geography as a science, in other words, the language of geography. Educational geography, like scientific geography, is impossible without a map. A map is one of the main sources of geographic information. The initial cartographic preparation is provided by the initial course. In the introduction, the concept of geography as a science is given, its importance for rational nature management and environmental protection is shown, and the history of the development of science is briefly described. The first section - topographic and cartographic - contains a system of topographic and cartographic knowledge.

The concepts of the terrain plan and geographical map are assimilated. A map is a reduced, conditional, generalized, distorted image of the Earth's surface on a plane. The concepts of scale, various ways of expressing it, the degree grid, geographical coordinates are assimilated. Students will learn about the division of maps by territory coverage, scale, content. Cartographic knowledge enables students to consciously relate to the map and use it to gain new knowledge[15].

A system of general concepts in physical geography, the concept of land and water surface, various types of land, parts of the World Ocean, relief, its main forms, land waters, meteorological elements, weather and climate, air masses, atmospheric fronts, climate-forming

factors, soils is given. Fundamentals of socio-economic geography. The concepts of the political map, the difference of states, the races of mankind, the structure and movement of the population, its location, natural resources and their types, individual industries and agriculture, modes of transport are given. This is a continuation of the initial geography course.

The general geographical overview includes the general geographical patterns of the nature of the Earth, the modern population of the world and its economic activities. Continents are studied in the following sequence: Africa, Australia and Oceania, Antarctica, South America, North America, Eurasia. Geographical location, history of discovery and research, natural conditions and resources, political map, population and its economic activity, individual countries are studied for each continent. The largest continent — Eurasia — is considered not only in general terms, but also in individual large regions. There are East and Central Asia, Uzbekistan, South and Southeast Asia, Southwest Asia, Kazakhstan and Central Asia, the Caucasus, Southern Europe, Northern Europe, Central Europe, Russia. Geographical location, history of discovery and research, natural conditions and resources, political map, population and its economic activity, individual countries are studied for each continent. The largest continent — Eurasia — is considered not only in general terms, but also in individual large regions. There are East and Central Asia, Uzbekistan, South and Southeast Asia, Southwest Asia, Kazakhstan and Central Asia, the Caucasus, Southern Europe, Northern Europe, Central Europe, Russia[6].

The content of school geography includes geographical knowledge, skills and worldview ideas. Knowledge is a reflection in the consciousness of the objective world, expressed in verbal form. Geographical knowledge is a reflection in the consciousness of geographical reality, expressed in verbal form.

Empirical knowledge expresses the external features of objects and phenomena. Empirical knowledge includes representations and facts. Representations are sensory—visual images of objects and phenomena in consciousness, memory, which are not currently perceived by the senses. This is an image of a phenomenon, an object in memory, which can be bright or fuzzy. Depending on how the representations were created, there is a distinction between memory representations and imagination representations.

Memory representations are images of those objects and phenomena that were perceived by the senses in the past. Imaginative representations are images of objects that have never been perceived by the senses, but created by the constructive activity of consciousness. There are also general and individual representations.

General representations are a generalized image of a homogeneous group of objects and phenomena. Single representations are the image of single objects and phenomena in memory. Geographical objects occupy a vast territory. They are characterized by size, shape, location. The image of the territory is a territorial representation. Geographical representations are mainly formed on the basis of a geographical map.

With the help of a map, we can survey the entire earth's surface, judge the relative position of objects, their shape, size. The image of the map in memory is a cartographic representation. The formation of a representation is the initial stage of training. Theoretical knowledge is created on the basis of representations, the essence of objects and phenomena is revealed, patterns are established. Facts — various information about the size, age, structure, composition of objects, dates, geographical nomenclature. They, like representations, serve to form theoretical knowledge.

Theoretical knowledge reflects the essence of objects and phenomena, their connections and relationships. They occupy the main place in school geography. The scientific level of the content of school geography depends on theoretical knowledge. Theoretical knowledge includes concepts, causal relationships, patterns, theories.

Concepts are the main and main particle of theoretical knowledge. Systematized concepts are mainly geographical knowledge. Concepts are a reflection in the consciousness of the essence of geographical objects, their most characteristic properties, signs, features, connections, relationships between objects. Concepts are formed on the basis of representation as a result of abstract thinking. There are general and individual concepts. General concepts express the essence of a homogeneous group of objects and phenomena. The content of the general concept is revealed in its definition.

There are general scientific and general geographical concepts in geography. General geographical concepts include relief, its various forms, climate, weather, etc. They form the scientific foundation of school geography. Individual concepts reflect the essence of individual objects or phenomena. The content of these concepts is revealed in the description of the characteristics of geographical objects according to a certain plan. The material for the description is mainly taken from a geographical map. Individual concepts have their own geographical names.

Geography operates with a complex of cause-and-effect relationships. Patterns express the most significant, repetitive, stable connections and relationships between objects, processes, phenomena and are characterized by a high level of theoretical generalization. Regularity is something that is characteristic of many geographical objects and phenomena. One of the main regularities is latitudinal zonality and altitude zonality (natural conditions and complexes vary from the equator to the poles and from the foot of the mountains to the peaks).

In economic geography, patterns include the principles of the placement of individual branches of production. Theories are the basic laws of objects of nature or society. In school geography, theories are mainly presented in the course of general geography (the doctrine of the geographical complex, geographical zoning, geographical envelope, etc.). As mentioned earlier, the components of the content of school geography also include skills and worldview ideas.

Skills are the ways of activity through which students operate with the acquired knowledge, apply them to solve educational problems and gain new knowledge. Skills are methods of activity performed automatically. The main ones in educational geography are cartographic and local history skills (skills in reading maps, studying local geographical objects). Geographical knowledge, skills and abilities are developed through the methods of academic work[8].

Acceptance of academic work means the order, plan, sequence of actions when working with a particular source of geographical information. For example, the description of the mountains on the map includes the following actions: find the location of the mountains, in which part of the continent they are located, determine the extent of the mountains by the degree grid, measure the extent of the mountains by scale and degree grid, set the prevailing heights of the mountains by the elevation scale, the maximum height by the elevation marks, determine the geographical coordinates of the maximum dots. Worldview ideas are a philosophical generalization of geographical knowledge. They are divided into dialectical-materialistic, political-economic and ecological.

Intra-subject connections mean the coordinated study of individual courses of school geography. Each subsequent course is based on the previous one. The knowledge of the previous course is developed in subsequent courses. There is no knowledge in the content of school geography that would not be developed from course to course. Therefore, a geography teacher should know the content of all school geography.

DISCUSSION

There are various knowledge systems in school geography courses: a system of topographic and cartographic knowledge, geogeomorphological, hydrological, climatic, biogeographic, ecological, economic and geographical, a system of knowledge on social geography, etc. These systems are also evolving from course to course.

For example, the initial knowledge about the relief, its basic forms are given in the initial geography course. This knowledge is deepened and expanded when studying the geography of continents and countries (the internal structure of continents, the features of their relief are studied)

In the subsequent course, the concept of tectonic structures, geological chronology and geochronological table is given, the influence of ancient glaciation and geological structure on the formation of the relief of Uzbekistan is revealed, the main forms of relief are characterized. In the course of general geography, the system of geological and geomorphological knowledge deepens and expands, the material is presented at a higher scientific level.

When studying any school topic, it is necessary to identify what knowledge students have on this topic, and then proceed to the study of new material. Interdisciplinary communication is the coordinated study of various school subjects. The implementation of interdisciplinary connections develops a broad outlook of students, contributes to improving the quality of knowledge, helps to develop a coherent scientific worldview, makes it possible to eliminate repetitions in teaching and strengthen explanations in geography.

The study of physical geography is based on natural science training in the subjects "Man and the world", "The Universe" ("Natural Science"). Knowledge of biology, physics, chemistry is also used, which makes it possible to better reveal the topics studied. The modern population and economy of the country cannot be understood without its historical development[5-8].

There is a lot of geographical nomenclature in school history courses. Work with maps and statistical indicators is based on the mathematical training of children. In the Soviet geography programs, under the heading "Interdisciplinary connections", it was indicated which knowledge from other subjects should be used when studying a particular topic. To implement interdisciplinary connections, you need to know the content of other school subjects. Geography surpasses other subjects in terms of the breadth of interdisciplinary connections, since it relies on the natural science and humanitarian training of students. The study of other subjects should also be based on geographical training.

The development of a consistent content of all academic subjects is one of the important problems of didactics. Each academic subject has its own logic of building content. Therefore, in practice, coordinated training is very difficult. Many questions of physics and chemistry are first studied in geography lessons, and then in these subjects.

Developing training. It is aimed at the development of cognitive abilities, at the independent acquisition of knowledge by the student. Schoolchildren learn to acquire new knowledge, work with various sources of geographical information. Self-acquired knowledge is

more solid and meaningful. Developmental learning includes problem-based, programmed and modular learning.

The essence of problem—based learning is the independent acquisition of knowledge by students under the guidance of a teacher. It provides activation of the student's educational and cognitive activity. Students get satisfaction from work and results, which stimulates the process of learning new knowledge. Problem-based learning promotes the development of thinking and mental abilities of the student. A necessary condition for problem—based learning is the creation of a problem situation.

The latter is defined as a state of intellectual difficulty. The student is not able to answer the question directly. He can't do it. If the student has realized the difficulty and is looking for solutions, the problematic situation turns into a problem. However, not every problematic situation can turn into a problem. This occurs when there is no appropriate training of the student to solve a problematic issue.

In this case, the teacher uses the method of problem presentation. He reveals the problem himself, shows ways to solve it, gives a sample of scientific research. In training, there are three types of creating a problem situation:

1. A problematic situation may arise when a student lacks the knowledge to solve the task assigned to him or when the task condition contains incomplete information. The student needs to replenish his knowledge and then proceed to solve the problem problem.

2. A problematic situation arises even when there is the necessary knowledge. To solve the task, you need to select the necessary knowledge.

3. A problematic situation arises when a student is faced with new conditions for the application of knowledge. Identification of the problem, its formulation is the first stage of problem—based learning. He poses problematic questions and gives problematic tasks: "What changes are possible in the part of the lithosphere where a volcanic eruption occurs?", "How does a volcanic eruption affect the atmosphere, the earth's crust, the hydrosphere?", "Why is the drainless Lake Chad almost fresh?", "Draft a railway line"[23].

Then follows the search for a solution to the problematic issue and the solution itself. The decision and the search for a solution is carried out by the student himself. The teacher does not give a ready-made solution, he can only outline a path, point out difficulties. The search for a solution lies in reasonable answers. The teacher follows the logic of reasoning, rejects or agrees with the arguments of the student. The most important thing in problem—based learning is the development of problematic issues and tasks on topics, sections.

In a modern school, only elements of problem-based learning are used. Teachers limit themselves to posing problematic issues when studying individual topics, sometimes posing particular problems.

Programmed training. This training arose as a response to the shortcomings of traditional training.

In traditional teaching, the individual characteristics of the student are not sufficiently taken into account. All students, regardless of their abilities, receive the same amount of information from the textbook and in the lesson. There are no differences in the way information is presented. But each student perceives the material in his own way.

In traditional teaching, weak and strong students mostly suffer. Weak students do not assimilate the educational material, strong students basically have nothing to do. An insignificant

place in the learning process is occupied by independent creative work of schoolchildren. Students receive knowledge mostly in a ready-made form. In traditional teaching, the teacher does not know how each student has learned the material. Knowledge testing is carried out sporadically. The teacher is not able to interview all the students in the lesson. Gaps in knowledge can be identified only after a long time.

Most of the learning process remains outside the teacher's control. In many ways, all these shortcomings are eliminated with programmed learning. With such training, each student independently learns new material, learns at his own pace, which allows for the individualization of the educational process. The training is conducted according to special training programs.

Programs can be in the form of textbooks or embedded in a learning device — an electronic machine. The training program consists of portions of educational material and a system of questions and tasks for its assimilation. Depending on the age of the students, these portions may be different in volume. Therefore, linear and branched programmed learning are distinguished. Linear programmed learning is designed for younger students. Portions of educational material are small. When answering questions and assignments, the student is limited to entering the appropriate words in the gaps.

The correctness of the answers is checked immediately. Branched programming is designed for high school students. Portions of educational material are more significant in volume. There are several alternative answers to the questions. If the student has chosen the wrong answer, he cannot move on. The program gives an indication of what should be studied. In some branched programs there are no ready answers. The student formulates the answers independently. There are programs with elements of linear and branched programming.

In our school there are only elements of programmed learning. It is mainly aimed not at obtaining new knowledge, but at controlling the acquired ones. With the programmed verification and assessment of knowledge, a control program is developed on certain topics of school geography. This program is a system of questions. There are several possible answers to each question, one of the answers is the most correct. The program is embedded in the learning device or multiplied in the appropriate amount (according to the number of students in the class).

During machine control, the machine itself issues an assessment. With machine-less control, the student puts down the corresponding question numbers and answer numbers when answering. In this case, the teacher sets the final mark himself. The programmed control makes it possible to test the knowledge of the entire class in a short time. At the same time, there is no element of subjectivity of the teacher in the assessment of knowledge. The disadvantage of programmed control is that it does not contribute to the development of students' speech. They choose ready-made answers, do not formulate them themselves.

Modular training. This is a new type of education in geography. The topic of school geography, designed for several academic hours, is divided into separate lessons. A modular program is compiled for the entire topic. For each module (lesson topic), an integrating didactic goal is determined, for example, to identify the features of the economic and geographical position of Uzbekistan, the features and specifics of its natural conditions and resources, population and economy.

The official name is the Republic of Uzbekistan. The state is located in the central part of Central Asia and covers an area of 447.4 thousand km².

The population is 34.6 million people. The capital of Uzbekistan is the city of Tashkent, which has 6.2 million inhabitants. Uzbekistan is a presidential republic. The President is the head of the executive branch, appoints the Prime Minister and members of the Government. In accordance with the results of the 2000 referendum, the President is elected for a seven-year term. The highest representative body exercising legislative power is the Oliy Majlis. The country is divided into 12 regions and includes the Republic of Karakalpakstan. At a lower administrative level, there are 141 districts, 124 cities. The official language is Uzbek. The national currency is the sum (since July 1993) [6].

The territory of Uzbekistan stretches in the interfluvium of the Syr Darya and Amu Darya from the northwest to the southeast. The north-western and northern borders of the country with Kazakhstan run through the desert areas of the Ustyurt plateau, then along the Aral Sea and Kyzyl-Kum with access to the Chardarin reservoir. In the east and southeast, in the most mountainous part of the country, Uzbekistan borders with Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. In the south there is a border with Afghanistan, in the southwest - with Turkmenistan.

Uzbekistan is located in the center of the continent, away from the oceans. The territory of Uzbekistan is one of the most flat in Central Asia. 4/5 of the country's space is occupied by plains, and only in the extreme east mountains rise. Between the mountains and the lowlands stretches a strip of upland plains with many temporary streams and rivers. This is the most developed and densely populated part of Uzbekistan. The ridges in the east of the country belong to the Tien Shan mountain systems in the north and Hissar-Alai in the south. In the extreme northeast, the spurs of the Western Tien Shan stretch - the Ugamsky, Pskemsky, Chatkalsky and Kuraminsky ridges. Gissar-Alai is separated from the Tien Shan by the Ferghana intermountain basin. In the north, it is closed by the slopes of the Chatkal and Kuramin ranges, in the south — the Alai and Turkestan ranges.

The eastern mountainous part of Uzbekistan is characterized by the highest seismicity. The strongest earthquakes (more than 9 points on the Richter scale) are observed in the foothill part of the Fergana Basin, on the southern slopes of the Hissar ridge.

In the central part of Uzbekistan is the Kyzylkum desert, occupying the interfluvium of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya. The southern extension of Kyzylkum is the Sundukli sands, stretching along the right bank of the Amu Darya from the lower reaches of Zeravshan to the southern spurs of the Hissar ridge. In the lower reaches of the Amu Darya, its vast delta stretches, an isolated uplift rises above it between the cities of Biruni and Nukus — the Sultanunzdag ridge — with a height of less than 500 m. In the extreme north-west of the country, at altitudes of more than 150 m above the level of the Aral Sea and the Amu Darya Delta, the Ustyurt plateau is located.

Of particular importance are intermountain and foothill basins, which are the main areas of irrigated agriculture. These include: the Ferghana intermountain basin, the Tashkent-Golodnostep sub-mountain plain, the Zaravshan basin, the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya depressions. The distribution of surface waters on the territory of Uzbekistan is extremely uneven. Water is used for irrigation, to generate electricity. There are more than 600 rivers in the country, and all of them belong to the Aral Sea basin. The main area of runoff formation is the mountainous part of the country, where the greatest amount of precipitation falls, and their evaporation losses are minimal.

The largest rivers of Uzbekistan are the Syr Darya and Amu Darya. They originate in the highlands of Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. Their tributaries also flow through the country: Naryn, Karadarya, Sokh, Chirchik, Zeravshan, Surkhandarya.

The Amu Darya is formed from the confluence of the Vakhsh and Panj rivers just 60 km from the border of Uzbekistan with Tajikistan. Having passed through Turkmenistan, the Amu Darya is significantly depleted, since, according to the interstate distribution, a significant part of its water resources is used in the economy of this country. Over the past 40 years, the water consumption in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya has almost halved.

The Sir Darya with its components is the second largest river in Central Asia, It is the main aquifer of the Fergana Valley and the Tashkent—Golodnostep oasis, through which several main channels are laid. Among the largest canals in the country are the Narpai and the system of canals in the Fergana Valley (Southern Ferghana, Northern Ferghana, Bolshoy Ferghana, Bolshoy Namangan, etc.). The largest reservoirs that have appeared in recent decades - Charvak, Akhangaran, Tuyabuguz, South Surkhan and Chimkurgan — play an important role in regulating flow and increasing sustainability water supply of the country's economy[5-7].

The main type of feeding of most rivers is glacial-snow, so the maximum rise of water occurs during the period of its greatest consumption — in the summer months.

There are lakes in Uzbekistan. There are two types of lakes — flat (river and irrigation system discharges) and mountainous. Flat lakes are fed by the water of rivers, channels, and they are characterized by wastelessness and ephemerality. Mountain lakes are moraine, blockage, and tectonic in origin. All of them are small in size, and their economic importance is not very great.

The largest lake in Uzbekistan, the Aral Sea, is also the biggest problem not only of this country, but of the whole of Central Asia. It is an object of ecological catastrophe. Over the past 35 years, from 1960 to 1995, the Aral Sea has not received about 1000 cubic km of river water, as a result of which the sea level has dropped by 17 m, the area of the water area has decreased by more than half, and the volume has decreased by 75%. It was divided into two parts - the Big and Small (Northern) Aral and moved away from the shores in places by more than 100-150 km.

A significant decrease in its size due to the drying up and high water consumption of the rivers flowing into it has led to significant changes in the natural environment (many fish species are disappearing, the natural regime of coastal ecosystems is changing) and in human economic life, which affects the social situation in the country. The problem of the Aral Sea has been studied for many years, but scientists have not yet found a reliable way out of this situation. More than a hundred types of mineral raw materials have been identified in the bowels of the country[16].

The main ones are gas, gold, oil, coal, copper, lead, zinc, silver, tungsten, bismuth, fluorspar, graphite, potash and rock salt, talc and cement raw materials. In terms of reserves of copper, tungsten, silver, lead and zinc, Uzbekistan occupies one of the leading places in the world. Of particular value to non-ferrous metal deposits is the possibility of mining ore mainly by open-pit (quarry) method. The ores of a significant part of the deposits are difficult to extract and difficult to enrich. This makes the development of their deposits dependent on fluctuations in the conjuncture on world markets.

Unlike other Central Asian states, Uzbekistan has all the main types of fuel resources.

Coal reserves are the least. The largest coal deposits are Angrenskoye (Tashkent region), Shargun and Baysun (Surkhandarya region). The proven reserves amount to over 2 billion tons. uzresurs population industry

At the end of the 1990s, 85 fields containing industrial oil reserves were discovered in Uzbekistan, of which 35 were classified as oil, 24 as oil and gas-bearing and gas—oil, 26 as oil and gas condensate.

Almost 60% of the initial recoverable oil reserves contain medium-sized deposits, the reserves of each of which do not exceed 10 million tons. Large and unique fields account for more than 32% of initial recoverable reserves.

Gas is the main fuel and energy resource of Uzbekistan. 134 of its deposits containing industrial reserves of combustible gases with a total volume of 3020.8 billion m³ were explored on the territory of the country. Experts estimate the total residual reserves of the fields explored for gas at more than 1883.1 billion m³. Gazprom signed a contract with the state company Uztransgaz for the purchase of 5 billion cubic meters of Uzbek gas in 2005. According to the monopoly, the total natural gas resources of Uzbekistan amount to more than 6.25 trillion cubic meters, including 1.62 trillion cubic meters in industrial categories. Uzbek gas supplies to Russia began in May 2003. In 2003, the volume of purchases amounted to 1.27 billion cubic meters, in 2004 - about 7 billion cubic meters.

The main gas region of Uzbekistan is Bukhara-Khiva, on the territory of which more than 90% of the country's total gas reserves are concentrated. The largest number of powerful layers were found within the Kashkadarya and Bukhara regions.

Of the fields being developed, two fields (Gazli and Shur-tan) are unique in terms of initial proven reserves, six (Zevardy, Dengizkul-Khauzak, Alan, Kokdumalak, Pamuk, Urtabulak) are the largest and four fields (Southern Kemachi, Shakhpakhty, Uchkyr, Kultak) are large. Experts classify most of the remaining deposits as small and only three as medium-sized.

Currently, the republic produces 55 billion cubic meters of gas per year, of which 5 billion cubic meters are exported to Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan.

Uzbekistan stands out among the CIS countries with reserves of non-ferrous metals, primarily copper. Three deposits are suitable for development in modern conditions: Kalmakyr, Dalneye and Sarychek. All of them are concentrated in Almalyk district of Tashkent region. The country has several more promising copper ore occurrences identified in Kyzylkum, in Southern Uzbekistan and within Karakalpakstan[3-7].

In terms of gold reserves, Uzbekistan ranks fifth in the world and second in the CIS (after the Russian Federation). More than 30 of its deposits have been identified here, whose total reserves amount to more than 4,000 tons. The largest center of gold mining is the Muruntau district. Individual deposits are located within the Tashkent, Jizzakh and Namangan (Marjanbulak, Zarmitan, Chadak) regions.

Uranium ore reserves remain significant. According to the data, Uzbekistan ranks seventh in the world in terms of reserves of radioactive metal, and its proven reserves amount to about 55 thousand tons

Tungsten deposits have been developed in the area of Ingichka (Samarkand region) and Koytash (Jizzakh region).

Among the mineral resources in Uzbekistan there are kaolin clays, ozokerite, sand, gravel, cement raw materials, as well as facing stone. There are precious and semi-precious stones.

The industry of Uzbekistan in the Soviet period was specialized in the extraction and processing of gas, ores of non-ferrous metals, mechanical engineering for the cotton complex. The chemical industry (production of defoliants for cotton, various types of fertilizers) was of regional importance. In 1998, the structure of industrial production was as follows: electric power industry — 19.2%, fuel industry — 13.3, mechanical engineering and metalworking — 13.1, food industry — 12.6, non—ferrous metallurgy — 10.9, light industry — 8.5, chemistry and petrochemistry - 5.2, building materials industry — 4.2% [6].

By stimulating the production of goods and services, the development of the foreign trade sector and the strengthening of monetary circulation, the introduction of new mechanisms for crediting enterprises, an increase in production in industry, agriculture, paid services to the population, and construction has been achieved.

Exports of chemical products, energy carriers, machine-building products, and food products are growing in the country.

The monetary incomes of the population are also growing, employment in the economic sphere is increasing.

All this gives new opportunities for the development of the country. New joint ventures are being created with other states, exports are growing, which creates favorable conditions for international cooperation.

Uzbekistan is located in the heart of Central Asia, between its large rivers Amu Darya and Syr Darya. The history of the peoples originally living in this territory has more than one millennium. This land has become the birthplace of a civilization that can rightfully be called one of the oldest in the East.

The history of Uzbekistan is the history of individuals and great nations, bloody conquests and large-scale uprisings, it is the history of the emergence of the most beautiful cities of Central Asia, it is the history of people who loved their Homeland with all their hearts.

For centuries, people lived on the territory of Mesopotamia, the most beautiful cities were built: Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, etc. They were ravaged by warlike tribes, but they, thanks to the efforts of people, rose again from the ashes even more beautiful and grandiose. This land was the place where the roads of the Great Silk Road intertwined, connecting Asia and Europe. Artisans worked here in numerous markets and bazaars, creating the most beautiful works of art that reached the most remote corners of Europe and Asia along the numerous roads of the Great Silk Road [6].

The history of Uzbekistan is rich, going back thousands of years. This, according to archaeologists, is one of the oldest human habitats.

It is known for certain that the territory was inhabited long before our era, even in the early Paleolithic, as shown by the finds, which are represented by found dwellings in the Baysun-Tau mountains and tools in Samarkand. In the late Paleolithic, Neanderthals lived here; their burial, discovered in the Teshik-Tash grotto, belongs to the Mousterian culture.

In particular, the burial of an 8-9-year-old child was discovered, which gives reason to talk about the oldest burial ritual of a person in Central Asia. The child's body was placed in a pit surrounded by the bones of a mountain goat. The finds at the excavation site allow us to say that at that time people were getting food by hunting and gathering. Primitive tools were made of stone, although tools made of wood and bone were also found, which suggests that the first attempts of ancient people to cope with the new material. 15-12 thousand years ago, the

transition to the Mesolithic began. Characteristic monuments are the primitive site in Samarkand, the upper layers of the soil of the Machay cave of the Baysun district, rock carvings in the Shibad district, and so on. For the processing of stone tools during this period, a person begins to apply the "method of pressing equipment".

Most of the territory of Uzbekistan is located within the Turan lowland, a significant part of which is occupied by the Kyzylkum desert. In the northeast and south are the foothills and spurs of the Tien Shan and Hissar—Alai (altitude up to 4643 m); between them are intermountain depressions: Ferghana, Zeravshan, Chirchik-Angren and others.

The main rivers are the Amu Darya, Sir Darya with tributaries; the Aral Sea. There are many artificial lakes-reservoirs. The soils are mainly gray-earth and gray-brown. Desert vegetation prevails on the plains, in the mountains — steppes, forests, mountain meadows. In Uzbekistan, 10 nature reserves have been created, the largest is Chatkal. People's Park of Uzbekistan. The educational material of the module is divided into separate semantic parts — educational elements. For each educational element, a private didactic goal is determined, and instructions are given to students on the independent assimilation of educational material (read from a textbook, analyze a table, diagram, map of the educational atlas, etc.). For each portion, the assimilation of the material in the form of questions, tasks, tests is checked. Any kind of independent work of a student is evaluated in points. Before studying the module, an entrance control is carried out (the basic knowledge necessary for studying a new topic is revealed). After studying the topic — output control (the assimilation of the studied material is checked). Homework is given. The meaning of modular training is to teach students to study independently.

CONCLUSION

The solution of this problem is facilitated by the fact that the educational material corresponds to one lesson, and various methods of orientation and organization of cognitive activity of students are used in the text. A great help to the teacher in preparing the lesson is provided by the program, where a list of what students should know and be able to do is given for each topic. First of all, the main scientific and ideological content of the lesson is highlighted. The educational material is divided into semantic parts.

In each part, the main, basic educational material is determined (leading concepts, basic facts, the most significant cause-and-effect relationships and dependencies, important patterns) and auxiliary. In most cases, not all the textbook material is explained in class due to limited time, some of it is studied by students at home. In high school, the proportion of this material increases. A simple topic can be fully studied by students on their own. The teacher determines which educational material will be studied with his help, and which one independently. The previously received training of students in geography and other academic subjects is taken into account.

For each semantic part, it is planned to work with various sources of geographical knowledge. The most difficult questions of the topic are explained by the teacher. Selection of teaching methods and tools. The choice of methods and means of teaching depends on the goals and content of the teaching material of the lesson, the preparation of students, their age characteristics. In addition, the availability of training facilities is also taken into account.

Depending on these conditions, explanatory-illustrative, reproductive, partially search and research methods, problem-based learning are used. The choice of methods also depends on the

place of the topic in this geography course. During training, the range of knowledge and skills is expanded, previously acquired knowledge is deepened and systematized, the experience of creative activity of students is acquired, which allows performing various independent work and acquiring new knowledge. For example, when studying Eurasia, schoolchildren can independently compile characteristics of territories based on standard plans and geographical maps known to them, widely using the method of comparison with previously studied continents. When determining the methods of teaching, the age characteristics of students are necessarily taken into account. Since younger schoolchildren are characterized by unstable attention and rapid fatigue, the teacher diversifies the methods and techniques of academic work, switches students from one type of activity to another, uses game elements (the technique of traveling on a map, geographical crosswords, lotto, puzzles, etc.).

In high school, as already mentioned, a lecture is used, which corresponds to the cognitive capabilities of schoolchildren of this age. In awakening students' interest in learning activities in the lower grades, a great role belongs to the entertainment of learning; in the upper grades, the creation of problematic situations that contribute to the intellectual development of schoolchildren is especially important. When planning a lesson, the teacher necessarily takes into account the time costs associated with the application of each teaching method.

Therefore, in most of the lessons (except for special lessons of independent work) students' independent work is combined with the teacher's presentation — the latter is the most time-saving. Teaching methods for each lesson should be selected taking into account the planning of the entire topic; at the same time, it is important to ensure that the system of lessons on the topic would sufficiently present creative teaching methods — partially search, research and problem-based learning.

When selecting teaching tools for a lesson, the teacher determines at what stage of the lesson, for what purpose and how certain teaching tools will be used. It is especially important to provide questions and tasks that allow students to independently extract knowledge from various learning tools to form ideas and concepts, identify cause-and-effect relationships, and develop the ability to work with this source of geographical knowledge.

The teacher finds out which teaching methods are planned to use various visual aids, which cognitive activity of students will be organized on the basis of these teaching tools. Special attention should be paid to the use of visual aids and other teaching aids as an independent source of knowledge and a means of developing students' cognitive independence.

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